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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 7.6 – DESIGN GUIDELINES AND VALIDATION REPORTS FOR PRIVACY [FINAL VERSION]

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Executive summary

The document summarises the results of Task T7.4: "Definition of Privacy Guidelines." This task builds on the work presented in D2.3, which focused on identifying privacy requirements related to the project. The guidelines were developed based on the requirements and an extensive analysis of related literature on the principles of designing for accountable and ethical Extended Reality (XR). We took the next step to validate the technologies against industrial benchmarks for ethical work, transparency, and privacy. We also conducted a series of workshops and large-scale studies with end-users to understand their perception of the main ethical tensions in their work. It helped us to understand ethical "red lines", which our solutions should never cross, as this would affect acceptance and could potentially create an unethical workflow. These results are outlined in detail in D3.8 We designed these guidelines to be applicable in the context of designing XR solutions for industrial work, focusing on off-highway machinery context. The results of this deliverable prompted continuous privacy-related development in the project, informing the assessment criteria in D6.7. The document comprises the following sections:

- An overview of current approaches to ethical and security guidelines in XR;
- A list of challenges in developing of XR solutions for Off-Highway machinery;
- The final version of the Guidelines in a graphical, easy-to-print form with detailed commentary about the content and the link to the revision history

Compared to D7.3 the document has major changes in the following sections:

- Section 2.1 expanded to include the descriptions of the EU Projects, which also extensively addressed ethics and privacy questions in their work (XR4Human¹, ShareSpace²); we also outline collaboration with these projects in the following development section. In addition, we also expanded the Related Works part, including several new papers, dedicated to the topic; similarly, we updated the section dedicated to industrial XR with papers issued in 2024 and 2025.
- We updated the Methodology in Section 4 by the procedures which were put in place from the Summer of 2024 till December 2025.
- We updated Section 5 with the final version of the Guidelines and explained the reasoning behind the final list.

¹ <https://xr4human.eu>

² <https://sharespace.eu>

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1 Introduction

The integration of Extended Reality (XR) elements into work contexts is becoming an important component of the transition to Industry 4.0 (and key step for building Industry 5.0 [28]). For example, XR is being implemented in various job processes, such as assembly, maintenance, and industrial training [8, 53]. However, while these applications benefit the industry and help improve various aspects of work, they can also negatively impact the privacy and security of workers and bystanders. When discussed within the broader context of XR, practitioners and scholars often mention the adversarial effects of XR on privacy [37,52]. This concern arises due to extensive data collection, including sensitive biometric data (e.g., gaze patterns [44], micromovements [41]) without explicit consent and with purposes that benefit companies but not users. Implementing XR in the workplace (especially in the context of industrial machinery) introduces additional challenges for developers. Newly developed XR solutions should be integrated into existing organisational or technological workflows. This integration requires an additional analysis of existing organisational and technological processes and requirements to ensure that new technologies will not disrupt current operations and aggravate working conditions. As XR technologies are still relatively new [6] in industrial applications compared to other sectors, such as entertainment, stakeholders are typically sceptical (e.g., [18]). This happens especially in industries with previously low levels of digitalisation, such as certain off-highway machinery sectors. The low to moderate digitalisation levels also implies that introducing new XR technologies, such as “always-on” sensors or cameras, could significantly increase the collection of personal data from workers and bystanders in the industries where previously these risks did not exist. In this respect, the organisations should rethink their privacy and data protection governance documents as the current policy may not cover this new practice. Moreover, the collected data about working processes can potentially be used to assess employee performance. That means, the extensive data collection enabled by XR creates serious ethical questions about the balance between operational efficiency (business interests) and employees’ rights to privacy and other human rights in the workplace. All the mentioned issues require a systematic approach to a) identify and b) specify and structure the main ethics and privacy-related challenges, which are relevant to specific industries. Several research groups and public organizations (e.g., XRSI[26], Metaverse Standard Forum [36]) have started to propose and promote general guidelines for the development of XR applications, but only a few of them, including EU projects, have focused on the ethical values and principles that should be integrated into XR-powered solutions [26,35,48,55]. Moreover, the general XR-related recommendations may not be fully applicable to the specific challenges in the workplace or may have missed some domain-specific problems. Therefore, we need to perform domain-relevant analysis to identify gaps where general guidelines may not work or may not prioritise enough specific challenges. To achieve this goal, researchers must collaborate with industry experts and other stakeholders. To our knowledge, there are no existing guidelines that focus on how to incorporate ethical work principles and privacy considerations into the development of industrial XR in the off-highway machinery context. Building on our work on privacy and ethics in the frames of THEIA^{XR} project, we provided and verified guidelines for the process of developing XR-related workplace enhancements.

2 Privacy and ethics questions in Extended Reality

Several studies have shown that XR can pose significant risks to user privacy, security, and their ethical use [3,17,22,27,45]. The first group of concerns is related to the problem of user identification in XR applications. The applications gather a significant amount of user behaviour data (often without the user's explicit consent) that may lead to the possibility of identifying them [16,25]. In addition, as many XR applications are tied to other databases (like profiles on Meta), it is possible not just to identify the user by their behaviour and biometrics, but also link this identified profile to other data types: the name, profile photo or geography [25,35]. Therefore, it is possible to use this combined profile for multiple purposes [25,35]. while also creating a risk of pushing users to overshare/disclose more personal information, similar to what happened in non-XR social media domains [22]. Overall, as [27] points out, unintentional disclosure of confidential data, the complexity of obtaining informed consent, and emerging vulnerabilities for attacks, are critical privacy and security risks in XR. These identified ethical issues can be grouped as surveillance concerns from users to organisations. In this context, the behavioural information gathered from XR interactions can be used against the user's interests. For example, micromovement data can be analysed from a health perspective, leading to conclusions about the subjects' health, affecting their insurance. In these situations, the XR-based data collection can lead to discriminatory actions towards users [41]. On the technological level, most studies focus on eye-tracking technology [12,43], which has been on the market for years and has a clear data collection path. The associated risk is that eye-tracking helps collect sensitive user information, such as preferences and mental load, often without explicit consent [43]. Several studies are dedicated to the problem of privacy in wearables [45, 57]. On the user side, there are works dedicated to the lack of user awareness regarding data collection, opaque practices by XR developers, and potential manipulative tactics by malicious agents, exploiting these issues, and XR's unique characteristics [2,4,23,24]. Hadan et al. identified factors influencing users' concerns about data privacy in XR [23]. The system, which collects cognitive, emotional, and personality data, is perceived as "too intrusive". The study also showed an increase in users' discomfort if the XR device operated "in the background" as somehow hidden from users' attention focus. The perception of algorithmic unfairness in data collection also contributed to the level of users' discomfort [23]. The study of O'Hagan et al. showed low awareness but high concern among users about AR headset activities, particularly those related to the data of bystanders [40].

2.1 Frameworks and guidelines in privacy and ethics of work in XR

There are several frameworks or foundational papers that can be considered as frameworks/guidelines in the design of XR solutions with a focus on privacy/ethics. The framework and software implementation proposed by Reilly et al. aimed to synchronize privacy-related actions across both physical and virtual spaces [46]. The main features of their tool include a shared ontology for physical-virtual interaction, a flexible communication model, and interface mechanisms that support user experience across realities [46]. In another initiative, De Guzman et al. [13] summarised a list of security and privacy concerns and created an ontology, which includes privacy model attributes such as integrity, non-repudiation, availability, authorisation, and authentication. In addition, in their work, they divide the areas which should be defended as data input, data itself, data output, user interaction, and device protection. The XRSI Privacy Framework, developed by the XR Safety Initiative, focuses on assessing privacy risks, informing users about these risks, managing privacy, and preventing privacy-related incidents in XR settings [26]. The XRSI framework aligns its measures with major legal privacy and compliance standards. The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended

Reality [35] identifies key privacy challenges produced by Extended Reality: capturing the sensitive and behavioural data (which leads to the possible penetration of mental privacy), the adversarial effects on bystanders' privacy, total surveillance and effect on the perception of reality and propose a list of recommendations for developers in the form of suggestions from design and legislation perspective [35]. Norval et al. discussed how XR systems are linked to their environment and user actions [39]. The physical nature of XR (interactions in the real world) means that problems can lead to immediate and serious consequences, such as injury and property damage, which go beyond the usual data-related issues. Because of the severity of potential outcomes, it is important that the auditors can reconstruct or comprehend the system's behaviour and its context during operation. Therefore, Norval et al. developed and tested a framework with experts to assist in the development of the XR system, which aims to facilitate the capture and management of data, a necessary requirement for conducting audits [39]. Abraham et al. [1] explored the concept of fine-granular permission control for applications in XR. They found that such an approach helps users better understand the balance between system performance and data collection, allowing them to make informed decisions about their privacy [1]. The E3XR framework, developed by Lee and Hu-Au [30], evaluates XR technologies in three dimensions: ethics, educational efficacy, and eudaimonia (human flourishing). Ethics is defined as user privacy, autonomy, and avoiding harm. Education is described as interactive immersive experiences that enhance learning. Eudaimonia assesses XR's capacity to promote personal growth and social good, as well as inclusivity and empowerment.

2.1.1 EU-projects frameworks for Ethical XR development.

During the course of the project, we actively interacted with other EU project which has major work packages addressing the ethics and privacy in XR (more about this interaction is presented in the Section 4). We would like to highlight two projects, which output shaped the current discussion about XR ethics and affect the final version of our Guidelines. The XR4Human [55] project was a 3-year EU project, dedicated to creating the guiding documents for the responsible development of XR technologies in the EU. One of the outputs of the project was the Code of Conduct for the Human-Centred and Ethical Development of Immersive Technologies. The code of conduct mentioned 9 guiding principles: human-centred design; diversity, inclusivity, accessibility and equitability; trustworthiness and transparency; privacy and data governance; safe experience; identity and right to anonymity; sustainability; technical security and interoperability; moral dilemma resolution and risk management [56][pp.4-5]. Based on those principles, the project proposed the following articles (higher-level guidelines): user transparency by design (meaning transparency in data collection, use and straightforward path for users to receive guidance and provide feedback), data protection and privacy by design (designing for privacy-sensitive experience, respecting the rights of bystanders and designing tools for supporting users in their privacy choices); risk management by design (practices, oriented to the recognition of the risks and standardisation of the risks response practices across the industry), well-being by design (addressing the psychological effects of the designed features and call for designing for safety and well-being of users, paying particular attention to vulnerable groups), identity, personas and avatars (protection of users identities expression and protection), shared spaces (addressed transparency of multiuser interaction and mediation/moderation processes) and interactions with non-human entities and objects (physical world, responsible AI-agents) [56][pp.6-10]. The ShareSpace EU project [10] proposes a framework, called Good Enough Ethics [48]. The framework was inspired by the concept of "Good Enough Parenting" - the parenting practices which acknowledge that perfection in parenting is not achievable and holistically focus on family relations. Similarly, ShareSpace propose six principles for building "ethical enough" AI and Digital Spaces: family (including human attachment and trust for social cohesion), community

(including autonomy and privacy), world (relation with external political, physical and spiritual world via applying principles for justice and responsibility) [48].

3 XR applications in industry and in the domain of off-highway machinery

To date, a limited number of studies have been dedicated to the use of XR in the off-highway machinery domain. Even in existing research, XR is mainly focused on a few topics. For example, a systematic review of the literature by Zoleykani et al. found that most studies on XR in construction primarily discuss its application in the design aspects of construction projects, with very little discussion on operational aspects [59]. Although there is potential to apply XR in end-user applications such as operator safety training, these applications are considered mainly a subject for future research [59]. Similarly, in discussing XR applications in the agricultural domain, which overlaps with off-highway machinery, Fountas et al. mentioned benefits such as the teleoperation of agricultural tractors [20]. Nevertheless, they also noted that this has not yet been implemented in agricultural processes. In the broader context of creating XR solutions in manufacturing, previous literature showed that mixed reality (MR) and virtual reality (VR) approaches can be used in different manufacturing stages. For example, VR can be used in the design phase, while MR technologies can be used in the whole industrial cycle [19]. Most augmented reality (AR) applications in industrial environments focus on providing work instructions for manual assembly processes, maintenance, and training. AR is also used to improve safety in human-robot operations (e.g., by showing the robot's movement trajectory to the human) and in the broader context of on-site analysis, evaluation, and decision-making [14]. Vasarainen et al. showed a growing discussion on using XR to improve existing working practices, especially in stressful and dangerous situations. However, certain existing limitations, such as the level of precision and seamlessness of interaction, make the use of XR problematic in some professional fields. Also, because the technology is still very novel, it can push the operator to focus on the virtual aspect of the interaction and ignore the real-world signals, which can cause serious risks [51]. Summarizing the findings, we can conclude that while both industry and academia agree on the importance of XR technologies for the development of industrial processes, including those related to off-highway machinery, the area is still underdeveloped and requires both further technological improvements and extensive user studies to understand the conditions of XR technology acceptance in the industrial context. In particular, in the domain of the ethical development of industrial XR, the systematic literature review showed that while the topic of ethical development of XR applications is becoming quite present in the related literature, the coverage is still mostly theoretical and does not have validation in related working contexts [11].

4 Development of guidelines for privacy and ethical work for XR enhancements for off-highway machinery

4.1 Methodology

Developing the Guidelines for Privacy and Ethical Work for XR Enhancements for Off-Highway Machinery, we applied the procedure described below:

The first stage (Development of Initial Guidelines) included the following steps:

- We conducted a series of interviews with end-users to specify their perceived needs for privacy and control over their data (described in detail in D2.3).
- We conducted a series of workshops in the frames of Value-Sensitive Design [21], the list of values we used was based on a short version of Schwartz values in the working context, built on [7,30,44] with end-users (N=13) to determine their perceived needs for privacy and ethical work; we also organized three workshops with other stakeholders and developers in the project to identify relevant privacy challenges in the development of XR solutions using the Linddun Go methodology [54] and GDPR-based questionnaire (N=10); (described in D2.3 and 3.8).
- We conducted additional in-depth interviews with industry experts (N=3) in each of our use case domains to better understand the state-of-the-art privacy and ethics in the industries and align future technological visions with the need to preserve privacy and ethics (described in 3.8).
- We triangulated the results of the expert interviews, stakeholders' privacy discussions, and analysis of privacy- related frameworks and challenges in XR, mentioned in the Related Work section.

On the second stage (Refinement and Validation), we continued the work towards better tailoring Guidelines to the project needs and collecting the external feedback on the Guidelines:

- We continue workshops with end-users to finalise the ethical dimensions, which should be reflected in the Guidelines (N=18) (described in D3.8)
- We made two workshops with project Consortium members to receive their feedback on the Guidelines and propose a way to update them.
- We organise and participate in several workshops, dedicated to the ethical tensions in XR development, presenting our view on Industrial XR development and prompting discussion about our Guidelines.
- To react on the project's developer concern about ethical use of AI in the project, we organised a workshop, based on Z-inspection methodology, where we checked if the project follow the responsible use of AI.

Our Guidelines did not focus much on the legal data protection aspect of XR-implementation's development, because like any EU project we are bonded to follow General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [42]. Instead, we focused on ethics-related user-centred design measures. We planned to provide medium-level design frameworks for domain-specific implementations. Following the approach to guidelines for designing for privacy discussed by Lederer et al. [29], we stress that our Guidelines does not necessarily guaranty the development of privacy-compliant and ethical XR-enhancement implementations. However, not following

them probably creates a channel for privacy and ethics breaches. Our Guidelines are compatible with more general XR privacy frameworks like XRSI and can be used as a complementary procedure for applying XRSI to the off-highway machinery domain. They are also related to the current EU propositions in ethics and privacy in XR development, as being in line with outcomes of other EU projects. We believe that our Guidelines will help spark discussions among different stakeholders across the off-highway machinery domain.

4.2 Relevant privacy and ethics challenges of XR development in the off-highway machinery context

4.2.1 Presence of bystanders at the operation sites

As mentioned in [35,41], it is critical to protect the privacy and identity of people in XR tracking operations. Although captured data may not inherently violate privacy expectations, previous work shows that if these data are combined with existing extensive databases (such as social media platforms [25]), they create significant privacy risks. In the case of off-highway machinery, the risk of collecting bystander data is high, as some of the XR-equipped machines are planned to operate in semi-enclosed areas of everyday city landscapes. Workers or the general public may be present and captured by XR solutions without their explicit consent. The bystanders are probably would not being aware of the presence of the technology, as the technology just started to be introduced in industrial settings, so the understanding of privacy risks is expected to be very limited. Although previous work discussed some ways to inform people about data collection in the area [32], the industry is still not yet discussing their applicability in the context. An additional challenge is that on the construction site, it can be difficult to draw a clear line between bystanders, who have legitimate rights to be on the place and trespassers, who are violating the safety (and possibly legal) requirements by being here. The situation creates a significant ethical question: should the technologies, by default, protect the privacy of trespassers, or should they prevent the operation site requirements violations by deliberately collecting this information.

Challenges identified:

- How can a bystander be informed of the usage and tracking of XR technologies?
- How to differentiate between bystanders and trespassers?
- What are the regulatory challenges for privacy and data protection in this context?

4.2.2 State of the art for digitalization in the industry and existing business processes

The interviews with experts showed that the level of digitalization in different areas of off-highway machinery is not yet high and may distinctly vary from one service provider to another. In all three discussed use cases, experts mentioned that the ongoing discussion about common data-sharing protocols and a standardised approach to developing technologies is still a continuous process. That raises a question of how to organically integrate XR processes into existing business processes within an organisation. From the point of privacy and ethics, it can be formulated as follows: a) how can we ensure that added XR practices do not create additional privacy risks compared to the existing baseline of the working process and b) how can we be sure that XR implementation will not create risks of unethical data use (e.g., performance evaluation without the worker's knowledge and consent) or unethical workflow (e.g., over-guidance or provocation of over reliance). The

question was mentioned by our end-users, and they are in line with the previous expert study of Ursin et al. [50] (in the context of a medical setting, which requires similar levels of concern).

Challenges identified:

- How do we take into account the different levels of digitalization in the domain?
- How to integrate XR technologies, without disrupting the business and creating new privacy and ethical risks?

4.2.3 24-Hours a day data collection

The multiple sensors and cameras in XR setups can increase privacy risks [35]. It is relevant in the case of off-highway machinery sensors as they usually run during full operation. Additionally, areas like container terminals or construction sites are usually monitored 24 hours a day to secure the space. This usage can raise concerns about mass surveillance and data gathering, which, in the case of augmented reality, presents problems with capturing private data from various actors.

Challenges identified:

- Can security requirements align with data minimisation goals?
- How can all workplace actors apply their data subjects' rights over personal data?

4.2.4 High cost of overreliance and other types of cognitive mistakes while operating the vehicle

When poorly operated, off-highway machinery can be a serious risk to the general safety of drivers and bystanders. The issue of misinterpretation of XR information becomes extremely dangerous in this domain. For example, previous studies have demonstrated the potential for cybersecurity attacks, which can lead to user mistakes and result in potential physical harm [9]. However, misguidance is also possible in the case of system errors without a malicious agent behind it. During discussions with end-users about possible implementations, experienced operators expressed concerns about situations where students extensively rely on features of XR systems without considering other parameters (e.g., machine indicators and weather conditions). Therefore, they might not be able to identify situations where systems misbehave or provide false information. This could lead operators into potentially dangerous situations. The lack of cross-referencing with real-world indicators could result in hazardous decision-making, which can damage the operator and the vehicle.

Challenges identified:

- What practices and design choices should be promoted to avoid over-reliance and encourage critical thinking?
- Which design patterns (in the context of GUIs) should be promoted to support appropriate levels of trust?

4.2.5 Use of AI models to improve the algorithms of XR solutions operation

There are multiple ways in which AI can be used in the domain of XR solutions for off-highway machinery. For example, it can be used to develop and update algorithms for collision avoidance [5, 38], optimise user

control and feedback during teleoperation, and provide real-time suggestions for performance optimisation [32]. Progress has been made in the domain of industrial robot teleoperation [34] and the operation of autonomous vehicles [33]. Yet, in the case of XR technologies for off-highway machinery, we need to at least fine-tune the existing algorithms based on the data from real operations. It can require recording an excessive amount of data from the operation side and storing additional data after the operation. These data can include bystander data that were collected without their explicit consent (as discussed above). Moreover, it would not be possible to take the data out of the system if bystanders requested it

Challenges identified:

- How to fine-tune the model, while respecting bystander privacy?
- What are the industry-specific challenges for AI?

4.3 Privacy guidelines: final version

4.3.1 Guidelines refinement via workshop with stakeholders

The guidelines were iteratively co-designed with partners to ensure their relevance and applicability, as well as to foster their appropriation. We organized an initial 1.5 hours in-person workshop where project stakeholders reviewed the definitions of guidelines and provided comments on their clarity and relevance. Then, they were divided into seven groups (one per guideline) to discuss in depth how the attributed guideline could be applied in real-world contexts.

A second 1.5 hour in-person workshop was organized to further refine the guidelines with a focus on the recommendations text. During this session, participants were again divided into groups and asked to evaluate the assigned guidelines on the following dimensions: overall perception, feasibility, and suggestions for improvements.

The list of versions with the anonymised comments from Consortium members and the development team is available on the visual board for the reference:

<https://www.figma.com/design/wicYdoH6c9wFkPZstnZ3Qp/Guidelines?node-id=64-2&t=xBicQmpxafU2LKup-1>

4.3.2 Guidelines: Privacy & Ethics in XR Implementation for Off-highway Machinery Context

Based on the input we received while working with internal and external stakeholders, we came up with the final version of the Guidelines. Our goal was to eliminate redundancy, disentangle several guidelines dedicated to the same topic (e.g., over-reliance was mentioned in two of the guidelines in the previous setting) and further specify the guidelines towards the context of Off-Highway Machinery. We also minimised the text on each Guideline, streamlined instructions and deleted long and wordy explanations.

The final list of Guidelines consists of 7 Guidelines, addressing the way to address the challenges which can rise while designing XR implementations for the domain.

4.3.2.1 Guideline 1: Transparency and Control

Guideline 1

Transparency and Control

Ensure that the XR functionalities are transparent and understandable.

Operators should be able to make **informed decisions** regarding their consent choice for data gathering (what is collected) and data sharing (who has access).

Guideline 1 - Transparency and Control

Figure 1: Guideline 1

4.3.2.2 Guideline 2: Data Lifecycle Anticipation

Guideline 2

Data Lifecycle Anticipation

Specify the role of physiological data from humans and data from space and surroundings areas. Implement data collection practices that are **ethically responsible** and **privacy-preserving**.

Anticipate and manage every stage of the **data lifecycle** (what is collected and why, data protection measures and deletion process...).

Identify XR-related practices that involve data collection. For example, if the project uses eye-tracking to monitor operator gaze, this should be considered.

Guideline 2 - Data Lifecycle Anticipation

Figure 2: Guideline 2

4.3.2.3 Guideline 3: Accountable Audit Processes

Guideline 3

Accountable Audit Processes

The XR-related data flow should be analysed to determine how much the collected data can be used for **auditability purposes** in anticipated and not-anticipated incidents.

The procedure of audit should clearly state **which stakeholders** are entitled to access to **which part of the data** and in **which moment of the audit**.

Audit process

- ✓ Clearly define the scenarios and use cases in which an audit should be conducted (e.g., vehicle underperformance, incidents, or predefined conditions such as zero visibility).
- ✓ Designate specific data points that are critical for auditing purposes.
- ✓ Define the role of the auditor who can check which specific data are needed for the audit purpose
- ✓ Ensure that the audit data serves the interests of all parties involved (e.g., can be used by the operating company, vehicle developers, and external investigators in case of incidents)
- ✓ Information about which data is audited should be clearly communicated, easily accessible, and include details on how the data will be used (e.g., for incident investigation).
- ✓ Operators should also have mechanisms to review or request deletion of their audit data where applicable.

Guideline 3 - Accountable Audit Processes

Figure 3: Guideline 3

4.3.2.4 Guideline 4: Awareness of Technology Limitations

Guideline 4

Awareness of Technology Limitations

Reduce the risks of overreliance and mixing virtual and real objects by fostering a critical mindset about technology's capabilities and limitations.

Ensure operators fully understand how the features work and are able to identify boundaries of trustworthiness.

System

Analyze XR feature to identify any aspects that might lead operators to misinterpret or overly depend on virtual information.

Is there a risk of...

- overreliance?
- reality distorted?
- complacency?

Operator

The operators should be able to efficiently control the process of operation and take their decision independently.

Implement training programs that focus on explaining...

- boundaries of technologies
- potential pitfalls
- optimal way of using virtual information

Guideline 4 - Awareness of Technology Limitations

Figure 4: Guideline 4

4.3.2.5 Guideline 5: Bystanders Data Collection

Guideline 5

Bystanders Data Collection

Address bystanders' privacy when collecting data from the surroundings.

Ensure that they are aware of potential data collection, especially in areas that may feel private. And when anonymization cannot be guaranteed, bystanders should be able to exercise their data rights.

-

Prioritize methods of information collection that are less privacy-invasive (e.g., using thermal cameras instead of video capture for human recognition).
-

Design mechanisms to protect the identity of bystanders, including anonymization techniques and cryptographic schemes for handling data.
-

Develop methods to notify bystanders about data collection; we suggest doubling the warnings to ensure they are not missed.
-

If data anonymisation is not possible, make a process for bystanders to request the deletion of their data.

Guideline 5 - Bystanders Data Collection

Figure 5: Guideline 5

4.3.2.6 Guideline 6: AI meets XR

Guideline 6

AI Meets XR

The development of any AI solutions for XR-related implementations in the off-highway vehicles domain should follow ethical AI principles.

This includes transparency, reliability, safety and fairness.

-

Prioritize the use of transparent and explainable algorithms whenever possible.
-

Test every algorithm implemented in XR solutions to identify and mitigate potential biases (e.g., the model should account for diversity in body size, shape if it's for human detection to ensure equitable performance across different individuals).
-

Ensure that the data used to fine-tune the algorithms for the domain of off-highway machinery does not collect privacy-sensitive data.
-

If the algorithms are fine-tuned on data from real operations, inform the operator of the use of the data for that purpose.

Guideline 6 - AI Meets XR

Figure 6: Guideline 6

4.3.2.7 Guideline 7: Human Always First

Guideline 7

Human Always First

XR development should prioritize the human experience by supporting operator's comfort, safety, and minimizing cognitive overload.

Ensure that XR empowers workers, enhances collaboration and contributes to a healthy and productive work environment.

Guideline 7 - Human Always First

Figure 7: Guideline 7

4.3.3 Intersection with Code of Conduct from XR4Human

As the EU Project XR4Human propose the Code of Conduct they developed as universal principles, which can be applicable to design in any domain, we made a crosscheck between the content of our Guidelines and the articles, proposed by XR4Human. The results are presented in the table.

Table 1: Intersections with Code of Conduct (XR4Human)

THEIA ^{XR} Guideline	Higher-level analogy in XR4Human Code of Conduct
Transparency and Control	Article 1: User Transparency by Design P5. User data transparency
Data Lifecycle Anticipation	Article 1: User Transparency by Design P1. Clear Purpose Statement
Accountable Audit Processes	Article 3: Risk Management by Design P1. Risk Management and Communication:
Awareness of Technology Limitations	Article 3: Risk Management by Design P4. User Guide
Bystanders Data Collection	Article 2, Data Protection and Privacy by Design

	P2. Respect for Bystanders
AI Meets XR	Article 7: Engagement with Non-Human Resources (in general, not specifically on responsible algorithm basis)
Human Always First	Article 4: Well-being by Design P1. Promote & Support Well-being

The analysis shows that the two groups of Guidelines have significant overlap, especially in the part, addressing data transparency and data protection/risk contamination. At the same time, we didn't have specific guidelines, related to societal issues in shared spaces with multiple XR users and identity safeguarding, as we believe these issues are less present in industrial XR. Therefore, we can conclude that our Guidelines are having complimentary character to the Guidelines designed in XR4Human and can be used as industrial extension of the core ethical principles.

4.3.4 Practical Use of the Guidelines in the Project

During the development stage of the project, one of the stakeholders raised an important concern on what should be our principal methodology to assure that we are following our Guideline 6, dedicated to ethical use of AI. To find the best mitigation strategy, we implemented Z-inspection procedure, developed by [58]. We run a 1,5-hour workshop with stakeholders, where we applied the method to understand the main tensions and difficulties which need to be taken into account while using AI in the project. We identified key tensions, which should be resolved through continuous discussion: the AI in the project is involved in fulfilling safety needs; however, the project is designed in a way that all the AI use is focused under the team's control, and we do not have situations where technological solutions work in an automatic manner without supervision. We also specify the number of issues which will be critical for post-project industrial use of the technologies: consent management after AI has learned from personal data, system reliability in non-standard situations, and workplace surveillance in case of multiple cameras attached. Despite the project members acknowledging the potential benefits of data collection for a better user experience, stakeholders decided to follow the minimisation principle in the collection.

In addition to the mentioned full-scale procedure, the Consortium members constantly asked the ethics and privacy team opinion about the ethicality of the solutions development, especially data gathering practices. In result project achieved most of its privacy goals as described in D as we constantly opted out to less privacy-invasive technologies, implemented all solutions in a basis of full operator's control, verified specific use cases of AI algorithmically tuning in the project as well as the methods for bystanders protection with both signals and signs to bystanders about collection and establishing technologies which hide the personal information of bystander as thermal cameras.

4.3.5 Presentations and Feedback

During the development cycle of the Guidelines, we organised several events to bring them into the focus of relevant stakeholders and initiate contact and inter-project work with other EU projects. Here we highlighted the activities of promoting the Guidelines and showing them to stakeholders in the Domain for privacy and ethics. The industrial XR challenges and possible solutions were presented and discussed during the following events:

- Workshop: Beyond Just Privacy: Addressing Ethical Questions in XR Spaces (EU Projects Experiences) which bring together stakeholders from the following EU projects: THEIA^{XR} (organiser), DIDYMOS-XR [15], SUNxr [49], ShareSpace [10], and XR4Human [55]. The result of the discussion becomes intense collaboration which later result in collaborative panel proposal (When XR meets AI: Data, Privacy, and the Need to Broaden Approach to Ethics, submitted to ACM CHI'26) and joint panel presentation on UnitedXR (Choose-Your-Own-Reality: Ethics, Identity and XR + AI);
- Workshop Purposeful XR: Affordances, Challenges, and Speculations for an Ethical Future (CHI'25, Japan, with short paper titled "Identifying Ethical Challenges in XR Implementations in the Industrial Domain: A Case of Off-Highway Machinery";
- Workshop: Do Tech Ethics (Actually) Work? organised by ShareSpace [10] project;
- Metaverse Standards Forum's Ethics Summit;
- Invited Workshop on EuroXR: Preserving Ethics and Privacy in the Dawn of Industrial Extended Reality.

5 Conclusions

While XR technologies are becoming visible in different areas, their use in the off-highway machinery domain is still relatively rare. However, when the industry will be ready to meet XR, practitioners should already have clear guidelines on how to implement these technologies in the domain in privacy-preserving and ethical way. Despite the fact that there are several initiatives, covering different aspects of XR ethics, it is still important to address the domain-specific questions, as not all the ethical challenges are equally present and equally important to the different domains. Our Guidelines approached the problem via analysis of existing initiatives in XR and the experience of XR development for off-highway machinery in THEIA^{XR}. We hope these Guidelines will be useful in further development of ethical framework for XR development in European Union.

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

AI	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
AR	AUGMENTED REALITY
CCPA	CALIFORNIA CONSUMER PRIVACY ACT
E3XR	ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK FOR ETHICAL, EDUCATIONAL AND EUDAMONIC XR DESIGN
GDPR	GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION
VR	VIRTUAL REALITY
XR	EXTENDED REALITY
XRSI	X REALITY SAFETY INTELLIGENCE